

Preparation of calcium magnesium acetate (CMA) deicing agent using waste eggshell as raw materials

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Abstract : Calcium magnesium acetate (CMA) was prepared using waste eggshell as raw materials, which had a desired deicing effect and could replace traditional sodium- and calcium-chloride salts deicing agent. Experiments showed 96.06% of CaCO₃ and 1.00% of MgCO₃ were the major constituents of eggshell. Regulation of the molar ratio of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions was 0.60, the total concentration of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ ions was 7.50 mol/L, the viscous paste material was formed when they completed chemical reactions with just excessive 30% of glacial acetic acid, CMA deicing agent would be gained after reaction production dehydration. It was seen the most appropriate ambient temperature of CMA used should be controlled more than -11 °C. Utilization of eggshell as the CMA production not only provides a cost-effective and environmental friendly way of recycling this solid eggshell waste, significantly reducing its environmental effects, but also greatly reduces the production price of CMA deicing agent using traditional methods.

Keywords : Waste eggshell, deicing agent, calcium magnesium acetate, recycling.

Introduction

Winter maintenance of roads often includes the use of deicing salt, which is applied to keep roads clear from snow and ice and to improve traffic safety throughout winter. In Sweden, the most frequently used deicing salt is sodium chloride (NaCl). The Swedish Road Administration (SRA) uses about 200000–250000 tonnes of NaCl annually for deicing purposes on national roads, with an application rate of 5–15 tonnes/km road¹. Nearly 20 million tons of deicing salts, principally sodium, calcium, and magnesium chlorides, are applied to U.S. roadways to provide less hazardous travel conditions during winter. Since these salts are inexpensive and effective deicers, numerous harmful effects result from their use². In general, deicing agents have been reported to have three main undesirable impacts on ground water quality : (i) chemical residues, (ii) oxygen loss caused by degradation of organic chemicals, and (iii) leaching of heavy metals from soils³⁻¹¹. But among the various compounds evaluated as deicing agents, calcium magnesium acetate (CMA)

has been considered based on its deicing effectiveness, reduced corrosion rates, and environmental effects. However, the use of CMA by various local and state agencies has been quite limited so far due to its current higher cost. Therefore, it is necessary to find other low cost deicing agents or reduce synthesis cost using waste raw materials.

China is a poultry production and consumption big country, with people's living standards improvement and the food industry development, the consumption of eggs has a significant increase every year. In 2007 China's egg output reached about 31 million tons, accounting for 43.9% of world production, accounting for the first in the world. Meanwhile, because the eggshell contributes 12–13% of the total weight of egg, about 400 million tons eggshell are often thrown away as waste every year. Thus, a lot of eggshell not only cause environmental pollution, but also cause an enormous waste of resources. The major constituent of eggshell is CaCO₃, eggshell as a good source of calcium has been reported in many respects¹²⁻¹⁸.

However, CMA deicing agent prepared using the abandoned eggshell as raw materials had not been reported previously to our knowledge. In this study, we provided a novel way to recycle waste eggshell by neutralization reaction between acid and alkali, and our target product was not a single metal or its oxide but CMA deicing agent with higher value. We also briefly reported on the synthesis process, the selection of calcination temperature and calcination time of eggshell, the determination of neutralization reaction conditions, molar ratio of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions and the deicing environment of deicing effect, and so on.

Results and discussion

The selection of calcination temperature and calcination time of eggshell :

Because CaCO_3 was one of the main ingredients of eggshell powder, and it was difficult to directly react with glacial acetic acid, meanwhile, an unpleasant odor easily gave off in the reaction process, it was more important that waste eggshell must be decomposed completely to CaO and MgO in order to synthesis CMA deicing agent. In addition, high-temperature calcination eggshell not only completely transformed the main ingredient CaCO_3 into CaO , but also removed a few number of organic substances in eggshell. Therefore, the optimal conditions of calcination temperature and calcination time for eggshell decomposed completely were researched.

The selection of calcination temperature of eggshell :

Table 1 showed the eggshell powder had different decomposition situations when it was calcined in muffle

Table 1. Eggshell powder calcined at different temperatures for 1 h

No.	Calcination temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Ashing appearance	Reaction phenomenon after HNO_3 added	Decomposition procedure
1.	750	Gray-back	Bubble	Not complete decomposition
2.	850	Gray	Bubble	Not complete decomposition
3.	950	Gray-white	A few bubbles	Basic complete decomposition
4.	1000	White	No bubble	Complete decomposition
5.	1100	White	No bubble	Complete decomposition

furnace at different temperatures for 1 h. Its appearance changed from gray-black, gray, gray-white to white with increasing the calcination temperature from 750 to 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Air bubbles appeared when the calcination productions of different appearances reacted with HNO_3 , which implied that calcination process was incomplete, also noted the existence of CaCO_3 or a certain number of impurities in eggshell powder. When the reaction temperature was over 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the reaction product was white, basically there was no existence of CaCO_3 in the calcination productions. Therefore, as could be showed that the eggshell powder sample could be completely decomposed when calcination temperature was over 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the muffle furnace.

The selection of calcination time of eggshell :

Eggshell powder after grinding was put into the quartz crucible and calcined in muffle furnace at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for different times, the decomposition circumstances were showed in Table 2.

Table 2. Eggshell powder calcined at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for different times

No.	Calcination (min)	Ashing appearance	Reaction phenomenon after HNO_3 added	Decomposition procedure
1.	30	Gray-back	Bubble	Not complete decomposition
2.	45	Gray-white	A few bubbles	Basic complete decomposition
3.	60	White	No bubble	Complete decomposition
5.	75	White	No bubble	Complete decomposition

Table 2 showed eggshell powder samples calcined at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for different times had different decomposition situations. The calcination time was 45 min, air bubbles appeared when the calcination productions reacted with HNO_3 , which showed the CaCO_3 in eggshell powder samples had not been completely decomposed. When the calcination time reached 60 min, no bubbles were generated, which showed the CaCO_3 had been completely decomposed in eggshell powder samples. Therefore, eggshell powder samples were completely decomposed into CaO calcined at 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at least for 1 h.

The determination of neutralization reaction conditions :

In order to make all eggshell powder samples and glacial acetic acid completely reaction, glacial acetic acid must be used over the range usually used. On the other hand, it is advantage to prevent the hydrolysis of calcium magnesium ions in drying granulation stage of CMA. Meanwhile, the concentration of glacial acetic acid had much greater impact on reaction rate and concentration time of reaction solution. If the concentration of glacial acetic acid was higher, reaction rate was faster and reaction process was more adequate. However, excessive amounts of glacial acetic acid should avoid wasted. Therefore, it was necessary to choose the minimum amount of glacial acetic acid used during the whole reaction. The experimental results were showed in Table 3.

Table 3. Glacial acetic acid amount on the impact of products

No.	Calcium oxide (mol)	Glacial acetic acid (mol)	Excess glacial acetic acid (mol)	CMA production (g)	CMA production appearance
1.	0.107	0.214	0	14.0	White, odorless powder
2.	0.107	0.244	0.030	14.3	White, odorless powder
3.	0.107	0.274	0.060	15.4	White, odorless powder
4.	0.107	0.304	0.090	15.7	White, odorless powder
5.	0.107	0.334	0.120	15.5	White, sourish powder

As could be seen from Table 3, when glacial acetic acid exceeded 0.09 mol, the excessive acetic acid not only had no positive effect on the whole neutralization reaction between acid and alkali, but also caused a waste of glacial acetic acid. On the contrary, when glacial acetic acid was less than 0.09 mol, neutralization reaction between acid and alkali was also incomplete. In order to improve the production rate of CMA, it was appropriate to be over about 30% the molar percentage of glacial acetic during the whole reaction process.

Molar ratio of calcium and magnesium, deicing environment impact on deicing effect :

Impact of molar ratio of calcium acetate and magnesium acetate on deicing effect :

CMA could be seen a mixture of magnesium acetate

and calcium acetate. Magnesium acetate was more soluble than calcium acetate in water, and thus higher magnesium and calcium molar ratio of CMA deicing effect was better. At first, it was a slow stage that the deliquescence of CMA absorbed moisture in the air and came into being solution. With the melting of ice and the formation of substantial solution, snow and ice would melt faster. Therefore, the melting capacity of CMA not only had a relation with its solubility, but also had a relation with its absorption capacity of absorption water in the air. A small amount of calcium in CMA did not reduce the overall solubility of CMA, and would increase the absorption of moisture capacity in the air in the initial stage of melting ice. Because of these two factors, the molar ratio of calcium acetate and magnesium acetate must be identified.

In order to determine the optimal molar ratio of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions, deicing effect test had been studied with the different proportion of CaO and MgO as raw materials. 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0 different molar ratios of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions deicing agent were made using waste eggshell.

In five different numbered beaker added 10 ml water, under the same conditions water was turned into ice in the refrigerator at $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and then 3.0 g of different proportion of CMA was placed in different beaker, respectively. 90 min later, the volume of water obtained by deicing effect test was showed in Fig. 1. When the molar ratio of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions was 0.6, the volume of water was the most and the melting ice effect was the best.

Fig. 1. The volume of water of different molar ratio of CMA in $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 90 min.

The choice of CaO, MgO concentration :

In order to improve the yield of CMA, CaO and MgO

should be converted to $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ before neutralization reaction. However, if excessive distilled water was used during the procedure, the time of duration evaporation for $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ converted to CMA would lengthen. The experimental results showed that the molar ratio of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions and the total concentration of metal ions were 0.6 and 7.5 mol/L respectively. CaO and MgO could not only be completely transformed into $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, but also easily turned into a viscous paste and was more favorable dried.

Impact of deicing environment on deicing effect :

The deicing effect was completely different for same deicing agent at different temperatures, 0.30 g of CMA added to the same ice (10 ml water used) to study the deicing effect between -5 and -19 °C, the volume of water obtained by deicing effect test after 90 min was showed in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The volume of water of molar ratio of 0.6 of the CMA in different temperatures.

Fig. 2 showed that CMA had the best deicing effect at -5 °C. The deicing effect was getting worse with the temperature continuously decreased. The volume of water fell sharply at -11 °C, and only 6.2 mL, was lower, the deicing effect was even worse than the traditional deicing agents under -19 °C. It could be seen the CMA used the most appropriate the ambient temperature should be controlled more than -11 °C.

Experimental

Equipments and material :

High speed universal grinder (FW80, China), high-

temperature furnace (SX2-4-13, China), inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (Optima2100 DV, Perkin-Elmer Corporation of USA), microwave digestion system (MAS, CEM Corporation of USA), icebox (BCD-250TB, China) and cryogenic refrigerator (model DW-YL270, Hefei Meiling Co., Ltd., China), eggshell (Xinxiang, China) were used.

Eggshell pretreatment :

At first, eggshell was rinsed three times with distilled water to remove the adhesion of soil and impurities on its surface. Then, the eggshell membrane attached inner surface of eggshell was removed when eggshell was immersed two days in distilled water. Finally, the eggshell was put into a dish and dried in an oven at 85 °C until the moisture was completely evaporated. After that, the dried eggshell was immediately grinded and eggshell powder sample as raw materials were obtained.

Composition analysis of eggshell :

White oxide ash was obtained when eggshell powder samples were completely calcined at 1000 °C for 1 h in high-temperature furnace, then, 0.30 g of the white oxide ash was digested with a mixture of 10 ml HNO_3 and 2 ml H_2O_2 by microwave digestion instrument according to the microwave digestion procedures optimized. After completely digested, the precise Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ion contents were determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES). CaCO_3 and MgCO_3 were the main chemical compositions of eggshell, and accounted for 96.06% and 1.00% of the total weight eggshell, respectively. Na_2O , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , P_2O_5 , Fe_2O_3 and volatile matter, and so on, only accounted for 2.94% of the total eggshell, values were expressed as % (w/w).

Neutralization reaction process :

The white oxide ash and an appropriate amount of analytical grade magnesium oxide were mixed. The molar ratio of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions was maintained at 0.6. The total concentration of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} was maintained 7.5 mol/L. $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ mixture solution was also made. Then an appropriate amount of glacial acetic acid was added to finish neutralization reaction between acid and alkali. During the procedure, the solution was continuously stirred using a magnetic agitator until the solution became almost viscous paste.

The formation of CMA :

After neutralization reaction, the viscous paste material was put into a dish and dried in an oven at 130 °C until they completely got dried. The resulting white loose powder, namely calcium and magnesium acetate (CMA) deicing agent, was obtained by the drying of calcium and magnesium acetate viscous paste material.

Waste eggshells were shattered with high speed universal grinder (model FW80, China) and were calcined at 1000 °C for 1 h in high-temperature furnace (model SX2-4-13, China). The white oxide ash was digested with a mixture of HNO₃ and H₂O₂ using microwave digestion instrument (model CEM MARS, America). The composition analysis of waste eggshell was studied by Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-OES) (model PE 2100DV, America). The determination of molar ratio of calcium and magnesium in CMA and deicing environment impact on deicing effect with icebox (model BCD-250TB, China) and cryogenic refrigerator (model DW-YL270, Hefei Meiling Co., Ltd., China).

Conclusions :

Calcium and magnesium acetate (CMA) deicing agent was prepared using the abandoned eggshell as the raw materials. The synthesis process was simple, the products obtained with high purity, safety and nontoxic deicing features. From the utilization point of view, the target product obtained was not a single metal or its oxide but calcium and magnesium acetate (CMA) deicing agent.

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